

Towards the European Commission's Road Safety Goal of 'Vision Zero': Intended Routes of the SOTERIA Journey

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Abstract

The emergence of complex urban mobility environments, where unknown interactions between different types of vulnerable road users (VRUs) and between VRUs and motorised vehicles, poses the need for a clear understanding of user behaviours, fair and optimised use of public spaces, as well as age-friendly urban safety action plans and assessments, capitalising on the benefits that technological innovations and the plethora of available data can offer in advanced accident analysis, towards achieving EU's 'Vision Zero' goal of zero fatalities on European roads by 2050. The SOTERIA Project aims to accelerate the attainment of this goal for VRUs through a holistic framework of innovative models, tools and services that enable data-driven road safety intelligence, facilitate safe travelling of VRUs and foster the safe integration of micro-mobility services in complex urban environments. At the operational level, the SOTERIA Project uncovers unexplored behavioural characteristics of VRUs and engages Living Lab communities (based in Germany, Greece, Spain and the United Kingdom) in social

innovation activities for the co-creation of urban safety solutions and infrastructure designs. Simulation models and explainable Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven analytics are developed for supporting policy decisions and informing interconnected services that support VRUs in safe and clean travelling. On-vehicle sensors and connectivity is fostered enabling minimisation of risky situations and behaviours. The approach will be validated in four thematic demonstrations within the SOTERIA network of cities (i.e. Chania, Dresden, Igoumenitsa, Leipzig, Madrid, Munich, Oxford, Wolverhampton), addressing different types of motorised VRUs (e.g. motorcycle, e-motorcycle, moped, e-moped, e-bicycle, e-scooter, hover-board (Segway), mobility scooter riders) and non-motorised VRUs (e.g. bicycle, scooter, skateboard and horse/pony riders, wheelchair users, babies/toddlers in prams, joggers, pedestrians). This article maps out the routes and inter-linkages of the activities and investigative axes that the project will take on its journey from 2022 to 2026, plus the expected impacts that will benchmark the project's successes.

1. INTRODUCTION

In response to on-going road safety concerns among European citizens, the European Commission (EC) has adopted ambitious road safety targets. In continuation with previous roadmaps (2010 and 2020), the EC has set a new 50% reduction target for the number of fatalities and serious injuries on European roads by 2030. This is an important milestone and stepping-stone on the way toward the so-called 'Vision Zero' (CINEA, 2022). Despite the Europe already being a world leader in reducing road traffic deaths and serious injuries, most efforts to date have focussed on the safety of car drivers and their passengers. In contrast, the safety of those outside vehicles has received far less attention – even though many deaths and serious injuries in European cities involve VRUs (WHO, 2009).

To reach EU policy targets, solutions addressing the challenges of a rapidly changing European urban mobility landscape with enormous operational uncertainties are needed. With ~75% of Europe's population residing in urban areas – an amount that continues to increase – the resultant accumulation of individuals in small geographical areas necessitates the utilisation of sustainable modes and micro-mobility services for the transport of people and goods, which is leading to increased numbers of VRUs. Moreover, recent reports show that micro-mobility is expected to experience a sharp increase in the coming years due to high trip distance addressability (60% of trips being <8km). Therefore, the ability to solve major city pain points (congestion, emissions) and low micro-vehicle prices that allow for rapid asset scale-up are necessary. Further, COVID-19 has had a strong impact on citizens mobility habits: recent surveys in EU countries report that citizens expect an increased usage of walking/biking and micro-mobility in the post-covid era (UNECE, 2020). COVID-19 has also caused an unprecedented growth of online shopping, generating the need for last-mile logistic practices where micro-vehicles have a pivotal role. Besides micro-mobility related VRUs, the challenge of an ageing population with a projected increase of older people (aged 65 years or more) in the EU to reach 129.8 million by 2050 (EUROSTAT, 2021).

Emergence of complex urban +environments where unknown interactions between different types of VRUs and also between VRUs and motorised vehicles is imminent. Clear understanding of users' behaviours and vehicle interactions in these emerging conditions, fair and optimised use of public spaces, as well as age-friendly urban safety action plans and assessments, capitalising on the benefits that technological innovations and the plethora of available data can offer in advanced accident analysis can be considered cornerstones towards achieving EU's 'Vision Zero' that entails zero fatalities in road transport by 2050.

The SOTERIA Project (co-funded by the EC and the United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) agency) aims to accelerate the attainment of the 'Vision Zero' goal for VRUs

through a holistic framework of innovative models, tools and services that enable data-driven road safety intelligence, facilitate safe travelling of VRUs and foster safe integration of micro-mobility services in complex environments. At the operational level, SOTERIA uncovers unexplored behavioural characteristics of VRUs and engages Living Lab communities in social innovation activities for the co-creation of urban safety solutions and infrastructure designs. Simulation models and explainable Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven analytics are developed for supporting policy decisions and informing interconnected services that support VRUs in safe and clean travelling. The approach is validated in four thematic demonstrations addressing different types of VRUs.

This aim of this publication is to describe the SOTERIA Project activities (structured into work packages (WPs)), reveal insights and goals of the Europe-wide case studies (Living Labs) and share the expected results of the project. This project's vision will be accomplished through attainment of six specific objectives that address methodological, business, technical and regulatory challenges, namely:

- Objective 1: To assemble interactive Living Labs across multiple European sites for expediting the co-creation of safety-centric public spaces by: (a) considering unexplored behavioural characteristics of VRUs; (b) understanding functional performance of new types of micro-vehicles; (c) capitalising on intelligence generated through advanced accident analysis; and (d) considering the impact of safety training on risk-free coexistence of road users and vehicles in such spaces (implemented in WP1).
- Objective 2: To develop a modelling and simulation suite supported by a constellation of advanced accident analysis approaches utilising a plethora of heterogeneous data sources, integrated into a safe mobility data space, and supported by explainable-AI services, seamless interfacing, wearable devices and data sharing across various stakeholders (implemented in WP2).
- Objective 3: To facilitate the safe travelling of connected VRUs through the deployment of a federated platform of interconnected services and tools that can determine risk-free paths, improve the visibility of VRUs to motor- and micro- vehicles, proactively inform VRUs of anticipated hazards and nudge all users to safer behaviours (implemented in WP3)
- Objective 4: To foster the safe integration of micro-mobility services in complex urban environments through better understanding of their demand, designing of situational awareness advisory systems and trialling of novel active safety solutions (implemented in WP2 & WP3).
- Objective 5: To deploy and assess the solutions in four representative Living Lab cities and regions, addressing varying EU urban contexts, social conditions, gather qualitative and quantitative results, and validate their effectiveness (implemented in WP4); and
- Objective 6 (O6): To accelerate the large take up of SOTERIA's results through continuous impact creation activities that assure the exploitation of the proposed solutions, and provide policy recommendations documenting the lessons learnt (implemented in WP5).

2. BACKGROUND

The project has several WPs (n=6), tasks (n=29) and deliverables (n=22) that aim to materialise these objectives within 42 months (2022-2026). The project follows a multidisciplinary approach, bringing together four scientific research institutions, four leading road safety solution providers, three policy-makers and city stakeholders and four cutting-edge technology providers. The project partnership spreads over seven countries with a network of eight cities for demonstrating the proposed solutions (Figure 1).

The scientific, technological and industrial feasibility of SOTERIA relies on the successful achievement of challenges and innovations in a number of key enabling areas including social innovation and behavioural analysis, transport safety modelling and planning, big data fusion and processing, AI and digital/Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. As such, this collaborative project applies a strong interdisciplinary approach, involving expertise and methods from various disciplines to create, develop and apply interconnected and urban road safety innovations for VRUs and micro-mobility users. The project partners are equipped with different capacities and knowledge in disciplines ranging from social sciences, transport and road safety engineering, applied urban safety solutions, social innovation, to computer science and AI solutions development, data management and sensory-based applications. Some of the transversal activities will be performed in collaboration with an extended group of stakeholders, while collaboration and synergies with other projects funded under the same call for proposals HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-01-06 will be sought. Expected project results will improve citizen's quality of life, as well as urban safety with respect to mobility; whereas, the acquired knowledge will be spread to facilitate skill transfer at an industrial, business, research and societal level. The urban safety ecosystem is also keen on open innovation, by engaging the society in dissemination actions (e.g. discussions on social media and in open forums).

Figure 1: An overview of the European SOTERIA project.

The SOTERIA Project establishes a Europe-wide safe mobility data space and specifically focuses on four demonstration areas (Living Labs), which are used to evaluate safe solutions for VRUs and micro-mobility services integration, while providing qualitative and quantitative information on the solutions implemented. The related data and datasets generated in the demonstration areas will be available for all partners, after being subjected to appropriate anonymisation and securitisation measures.

3. SOTERIA'S CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGY

The overall concept of the project can be seen in Figure 2. The developments of the project have been structured under five axes covering different research and technological domains, as well as actions for the implementation, augmentation and assessment of the solutions. Next, the different axes of the project are described in detail and explained.

Figure 2: The overall concept of the SOTERIA project.

3.1 Project Axis One: Co-Creation and Social Innovation Living Labs

An empirical baseline investigation of VRU needs, behaviours and preferences, using a sequential explanatory mixed-method design of extrapolating from theory to practice, will be employed to underpin the project activities. Adopting a phased research strategy of qualitative (world café workshops) and quantitative (questionnaires) data collection and analysis, typical of social and behavioural science research, will enable the capture of VRU mobility trends, relationships, and alliances, and refine details of specific urban safety situations pertinent to the circumstances of VRUs. This approach will allow the development of a taxonomy of needs and behaviours that will inform the technological developments of the project.

An integrated modelling and simulation suite will allow the development and evaluation of conceptual designs of public spaces. A system-level modelling module will utilise a data-driven accident analysis approach to model influential factors for different types of accidents and infrastructure elements. The module will integrate statistical and AI models and algorithms that will be developed in Axis Two (described below) of the project. A micro-level accident modelling component will integrate 3D-modelling tools and agent-based transport simulation software in order to accurately model the movement of road users and vehicles at public spaces; thus, capturing potential conflicts. The micro-level accident modelling component will incorporate features from the VRU behaviour taxonomy model for the accurate representation of the movement of the different agents. Finally, a collection of crash estimation models, underpinned by probabilistic models will generate risk factors.

SOTERIA's interventions will be conceptualised and designed as part of co-creation activities established through its network of cities. The establishment of the Living Labs will commence with the definition of the actors' roles with emphasis placed on the involvement of different types of VRUs. Furthermore, public (i.e. local authorities, public transport operators) and private (i.e. mobility service providers, data providers, micro-vehicle manufacturers) stakeholders with complementing interests in road safety will reinforce the value creation potential of the Living Labs. Co-creation initiatives will take place at different stages of the project for engaging with the stakeholders. Activities will conclude with a performance measurement phase during which the impact and effectiveness will be assessed.

3.2 Project Axis Two: Advanced Accident Analysis and Safety Intelligence

The project will develop advanced data intelligence solutions to support risk-free travelling of VRUs. A risk heatmaps defining module will utilise historical and real-time data for the formulation of high-resolution maps with safety-related parameterisation. These may include infrastructure design deficiencies, riskiness of road user behaviour and externalities (i.e. weather conditions). Maps will incorporate data-points based on accidents and near-misses and will have the potential to be dynamically updated with data coming from infrastructure and on-micro-vehicle devices. Correlation of accidents and near-misses will identify hidden causes that may lead to accidents (causes taxonomy), but are not recorded in accident statistics due to their difficult-to-identify nature. An advanced accident analysis module will utilise: (i) multivariate statistical modelling; and (ii) an AI-approach to allow the estimation of accidents' frequency and severity at different parts of the road network. Generalised linear models (GLMs) will be created per type of road network (section/intersection), manoeuvre type and other variables from the parameterisation of the heatmaps. Correlation analysis will give insight to interdependent variables and consequently, within the model development process variables will be chosen by their ability to explain variations in accident frequencies. As part of the AI-approach adopted for the SOTERIA project, different deep-learning algorithms will be developed and assessed for their appropriateness in estimating and predicting accurately 'risky situations' on the road network. Adopting deep learning approaches will allow the exploitation of unstructured data, the definition of spatio-temporal relations of different parameters intrinsic to traffic accidents and the identification of external influencing factors that contribute to potentially hazardous situations.

3.3 Project Axis Three: Increasing Safety of VRUs

The SOTERIA Project will develop multiple information services that will assist VRUs to minimise errors in their decision-making, avoid exposure to hazardous situations and receive

proactive notifications for potential hazards. A safe and clean routing engine will utilise: (i) estimation of expected accident frequencies along heterogeneous street links considering multiple influencing environmental, climatic, traffic-related, demographic, or infrastructural factors; and (ii) a weighing method to achieve a balance between time, distance, and safety as part of the route generation process. A dynamic personalisation module will accommodate needs of different VRUs and will allow the dynamic updating of user profiles based on current physio- and psychological attributes, using data from sensory kits. Route choice measures, based on the developed behaviour taxonomy, will be reviewed and used in the algorithms. A safety-oriented nudge engine will support user decisions towards safe travelling, extending behavioural change support technologies and persuasive technology approaches in the mobility domain, by infusing personalisation for different user groups in different contexts, based on big data information and the preceding accident analytics services. The nudge engine will include proactive pushes, communicated to travellers through user engagement applications including mobile apps with textual and voice interfaces. A dynamic risk hotspot service, supported by real-time stream analytics, will update risk factors. Situations of interest such as increased motorised traffic, flow disruptions events (accidents, roadworks) increased demand hotspots for micro-mobility and others will feed into multi-criteria frameworks.

3.4 Project Axis Four: Safe Integration of Micro-mobility

SOTERIA will develop approaches and technologies for the safe integration of micro-mobility to current traffic streams and infrastructure configurations. These will be grouped under two thematic areas, namely: (i) micro-mobility demand prediction and (ii) safety-centric micro-vehicle sensory kit. The former will exploit big geolocated data to obtain information on the travel patterns of the urban population, facilitating the calibration of travel demand models and the monitorisation of mobility flows. The primary data source will be mobile network data, which consist of the records collected by mobile network operators from the communication between mobile devices and the network antennas. The solution will use these records together with land use data (which allows improving the spatial precision with which records are located), passenger transport supply data, socio-demographic data and other available transport demand data that are useful to adjust the results. Data analysis will identify the location and duration of the anonymous users' activities, which will be linked to trips, which can be further characterised making possible the generation of mobility indicators with the desired spatial and temporal aggregation. Sensory kits will integrate a number of sensors, cameras, radars and microcontrollers on micro-vehicles, enabling the collection of heterogeneous contextual, vehicle handling, kinematics and environmental data.

3.5 Project Axis Five: Solutions Integration, Augmentation and Impact Assessment

The services, models and technologies described above will be integrated into a microservices platform supporting seamless integration of additional services, dynamic customisation of workflows, improved security and resilience and modular deployment in different environments. The SOTERIA Project will develop two types of road user information services: (i) a set of customisable and dynamic dashboards for spatio-temporal visualisations; (ii) a mobile app, with customisable interfaces to cover the needs of all various user groups. Furthermore, this axis will facilitate Living Lab activities related to: (i) the assessment of the pilot demonstrations and the incorporation of the findings into an evidence-based risk assessment framework, (ii) the consolidation of new micro-mobility characteristics and road user behaviours as part of future accident reporting standards, (iii) the rationalisation of the

demonstration outputs into regulatory recommendations and policy adaptation actions and (iv) the economic assessment of high-impact interventions and solutions as a read-to-use toolkit for future infrastructure investments and planning.

4. SOTERIA'S LIVING LABS AND DEMONSTRATIONS

The SOTERIA Project is setting up four Living Labs to support its investigations. Popular for finding solutions to real-life urban challenges, Living Labs can be a methodology, a system, an experiment, an ecosystem, an innovation intermediary and also a partnership. Designing and crafting Living Labs requires the involvement of a diversity of local actors, stakeholders, collaborators and networks; thus, they integrate the quadruple-helix voices of citizens, organisations/authorities and institutions (i.e. a type of public-private-people partnership), through a participatory activism of shared perspectives and knowledge exchange to develop environmentally, socially, economically and culturally robust sustainability-driven outcomes and practices. These forums are instruments of empowerment that enable the unravelling of unexplored human-environmental-technological solutions, scenarios and overarching co-constructed visions for conceptualising initiatives, encouraging innovative co-operation, improving efficiency and driving policy for the betterment of towns, cities and regions.

A literature search indicates there is no single standalone definition that has been adopted widely to describe a Living Lab. However, Zipfel *et al.* (2022) does suggest they can be characterised by five key components: user-centric, co-creation, real-life context, test innovation and open innovation. Beneath (boxes one-to four) are descriptions and insights into the project's four Living Labs set-up in United Kingdom, Germany, Spain, Greece and their specific goals.

Box One: The Oxfordshire (United Kingdom) Living Lab

Oxfordshire, situated in south eastern England, is home to ~640,000 residents. The county consists of Oxford city and four other districts. Oxfordshire County Council manages over 4,200 km of its roads, which are used by ~325,000 registered vehicles. Annually, an estimated 30,000 accidents of all types, around 30 deaths, 245 serious injuries and nearly 1,250 slight injuries are reported. The value of preventing these accidents and injuries each year is estimated at over 130 million euros. The local transport plan for 2015-2031 has identified the need for supporting active travelling initiatives in the region. However, successful attainment of the defined goals requires the introduction of solutions that will improve the safety of VRUs. The main goals of the activities in this Living Lab are:

- Apply social innovation and co-design activities involving VRUs to propose low-cost infrastructure interventions in Oxfordshire. The proposed interventions will be designed and modelled using appropriate tools and a pre- and post- safety impact assessment analysis.
- Investigate the integration of additional micro-vehicles (e.g. e-scooters) in the existing cycling infrastructure. This will be based on the identification of mobility needs of VRUs and micro-level behavioural characteristics under different contextual taxonomies.
- Apply advanced safety and accident analysis techniques allowing the spate-temporal decomposition of 'high-risk situations' with the use of an integrated active safety system ecosystem of devices and micro-vehicles sensors kits. This will be supported by the use of predictive analytics and pattern recognition as part of explainable-AI and by capitalising on data from motorised and non-motorised vehicles.
- Develop a dynamic safe mobility data space which will integrate data from various static and dynamic sources and will allow visualisations of diagnostic and prognostic safety assessment indicators in the context of 'live' risk hotspots and micro-mobility hazard maps.

Box Two: The Saxony (Germany) Living Lab

The Free State of Saxony, located in south eastern Germany, and has ~4 million inhabitants. Every year ~100,000 accidents are registered in Saxony, of which ~5,500 involve VRUs. Young people (aged 10–16) are

VRUs showing major changes in their mobility patterns and who are becoming increasingly active in their mobility behaviour, without, as a rule, neither sufficient awareness of the dangers in road traffic nor sufficient experience or sense for the perspective of motorised road users. This age group (often referred to as Generation Z) and their parents are smartphone and internet-savvy road users. Data of accidents in the proximity of a school and on typical ways to and from school provides the basis for piloting safe routing behavioural change and safety alerting. The main goals of the activities in this Living Lab are:

- Determination of risk in case of changes of location, whereby the focus of the evaluation is on accident or near-misses data as well as infrastructure data. Data will be taken, amongst others, from the Traffic Accident Monitoring (TAM) database (Europe's largest database for police recorded accidents established by F-IVI), supplemented by German In-Depth Accident Study GIDAS () data.
- Demonstration of the Safest Route Advisor for VRU (SARA-VRU). With the help of a web application and a mobile app for smartphones, the SARA-VRU-alert, young VRUs and their legal guardians, among others, can determine the safest possible routes for changing locations in advance or they are warned accordingly when approaching areas that are particularly dangerous for VRUs.
- Analysis of the availability of suitable accident and infrastructure data in EU countries as well as their comparability in terms of harmonisation of input data (accident, traffic data, infrastructure data) for incorporation into an EU-wide database and cross-border systematic evaluation as well as processing of accident data with the aim of creating the basis for SARA-VRU and SARA-VRU-alert as Europe-wide as possible.

Box Three: The Madrid (Spain) Living Lab

Madrid, the capital of Spain, has a population of >3 million inhabitants. In 2021, the Governing Board of the Madrid City Council has approved a new road safety plan. The plan has as strategic objective to move towards safe mobility with zero tolerance for accidents, and promote road safety habits that allow safe travel. The main goals of the activities in this Living Lab are:

- Improve the understanding of safety risks through visualisation, monitoring and analysis of road usage per transport mode by considering parking spots and origin-destination trips, identification of traffic intensity per road section and study of city accidents hotspots data to explore multimodal behaviours.
- Improve city infrastructure and increase safety for all road users by: (i) planning protected bicycle lanes and mobility hubs, (ii) establishing geo-localised speed limit regulations for specific transport modes, (iii) notifying operators when dangerous events are identified and improving road safety decision-making processes.
- Predict dangerous events through the identification and mapping of near-miss events, the classification of city areas according to the risks for VRUs, predicting crashes involving VRUs and estimations of which VRUs are positively affected by road safety predictions.
- Simulate the impact of infrastructure and regulations improvements, including the impact of reducing speed, changing a two-ways street into a one-way street, optimising parking spaces and implementing segregated bicycle lanes.

Box Four: The Chania/ Igoumenitsa (Greece) Living Lab

The demonstrations of SOTERIA solutions will take place in the cities of Chania and Igoumenitsa. Greece is the only EU country that achieved the decade 2010-2020 target of reducing the number of road traffic fatalities by 50%, but still ranked 20th among EU countries in terms of road safety. Increased road safety over the past decade is attributed to systematic initiatives by authorities; however, a significant factor has also been the deep economic recession which led to new traffic conditions, as well as to a less aggressive driving behaviour at lower speeds. In particular, in both Igoumenitsa and Chania, there are well-established public bicycle sharing services as well as power two-wheeler-based delivery services. Both cities offer ideal testbeds for evaluating the VRUs and micro-mobility safety services with a high number of diverse groups of users making use of public bicycles, including tourists, under complex traffic situations as both cities have a port and a complex network of roads connecting the city's centre with the port. The main goals of the activities in this Living Lab are:

- Reduce micro-mobility hazards, through the SOTERIA sensory kit for two-wheelers and safe routing applications by: (i) identifying areas with infrastructure deficiencies and vehicle conflicts; (ii) identifying and monitoring risky road user behaviours and (iii) providing situational aware speed advice, with proactive notifications to slow down when approaching hazards.

- Identify the impact of infrastructure changes, including the impact of reducing speed limits and implementing bicycle lanes.

5. DISCUSSION

This section discusses how the expected innovations, resulting from the project's objectives, will achieve the expected outcomes and impacts. A snapshot of the SOTERIA's pathways towards the expected impacts can be seen in Figure 3. The project's expected innovations can be consolidated to form the expected results, according to their future exploitation potential, namely:

- *User behaviour modelling and co-creation approach*: This asset includes a taxonomy of road user behaviours and needs of VRUs according to the micro-vehicles being operated, along with a co-creation framework for learning and participatory design of interventions.
- *Best practices, learning and standardisation frameworks*: This asset includes a knowledge base of best practices for road safety and a holistic safety training programme targeting the skills of various actors including designers, operators and users of transport systems accommodating the needs of VRUs.
- *Safe mobility data space*: This asset will fuse, integrate and harmonise heterogeneous data sources from different transport industries, sensors and services, and ensure trustworthy exchange of data and their interoperability, while keeping data generators in control.
- *Modelling and simulation suite*: This asset includes modelling and simulation tools for micro-level analysis and design of public spaces including micro-vehicle corridors, shared infrastructure and intersections supporting multimodality.
- *Advanced and explainable AI accident analysis and road safety intelligence platform*: This asset includes data-driven integrated accident modelling and analysis tools along with a suite of explainable-AI techniques for enhancing the trustworthiness of the generated road safety intelligence and communicating it to diverse user groups.
- *Safe and connected mobility services suite*: This asset includes a suite of safe travel services for supporting VRUs in their day-to-day travelling (pre-trip, on trip and post-trip) along with services allowing communication between VRUs.
- *Protective equipment assessment framework*: This asset allows the evaluation of the effectiveness of various types of equipment according to the status of the network (i.e. traffic density), the environmental conditions (i.e. weather, level of visibility, etc.) and the characteristics of VRUs.
- *Micro-mobility demand prediction services*: This asset enables the prediction of micro-mobility demand, including utilisation density maps for different types of users and modes, enabling proactive notification of road users for system-wide distribution of VRUs.
- *Micro-vehicle sensory kit with embedded situational awareness mechanisms*: This asset includes sensors and cameras supporting the collection of micro-vehicle handling, user behaviour and obstacle proximity data, along with providing situational-awareness warnings to VRUs about safe speed limits and potential hazards.
- *SOTERIA's innovations' evidence-based assessment*: Outcomes of the SOTERIA demonstrations showing the impact of the proposed solution in enhancing VRUs' safety.
- *Capacity building and policy adaptation instruments*: Policy recommendations are promoted to policy makers enabling a safer, more secure and accessible urban environment for VRUs.

These expected results will produce quantifiable project outcomes, highlighting the significance of the project’s contributions, which map to the expected outcomes of the EC’s call for proposals HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-01-06. The time horizon for the realisation of all outcomes starts during the pilot demonstrations of the project (at small scale) and lasts until 5-years after the completion of project, when by the potential of the project reaches its fruition.

Figure 3: The SOTERIA project’s pathways from results and outcomes to expected impacts.

6. FUTURE OF THE SOTERIA PROJECT

The expected impacts of the SOTERIA Project will demonstrate its long-term success, these are anticipated to be:

- enhanced local and/or regional capacity for governance and innovation in urban mobility logistics;
- improved reliability and performance of systems that aim to anticipate and minimise safety risks, avoiding risks and collisions and reducing the consequences of unavoidable crashes;
- a 50 % reduction in serious injuries and fatalities in road crashes by 2030;
- better design principles of future road transport systems enabling better traffic flow in big cities.

Further information and updates on the SOTERIA Project are available at www.soteriaproject.eu, which includes access to blogs and a regular newsletter, plus links to the project's reports, publications and findings.

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